

Data Domain Design: Interview Protocol

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1 Guidelines for the Interviewer

These guidelines are designed to help interviewers conduct structured, insightful, and consistent interviews. The purpose of this protocol is to ensure that each interviewer approaches the interview with a similar framework. By following the standardized questions and understanding the key concepts related to data domains, interviewers can foster a conversational environment that encourages deeper responses. This protocol also includes a prepared introduction to help set a welcoming tone and clear expectations for interviewees, promoting a productive and comfortable experience. Fig. 1 shows an overview of the steps of the methodology followed during this study.

Standardised questions. All interviewers will use a standardized set of questions. This approach ensures consistency across different interviews, allowing us to gather comparable data from each interviewee. By asking the same core questions, we can better analyse responses to identify patterns, trends, and variations in answers. Standardization helps reduce interviewer bias, ensuring that the focus remains on the interviewee's insights rather than variations in question phrasing.

Encourage conversational flow and explore deeper insights. While standardized questions are essential, it's equally important to foster a natural conversation during the interview. If an interviewee provides an answer that you find intriguing or insightful, feel free to explore that topic further with follow-up questions. This open-ended approach allows the interview to reveal additional perspectives or details that might not emerge from strictly sticking to the predefined questions. However, ensure that any follow-up questions remain relevant to the interview's primary focus.

Review background theory on data domains. Before conducting interviews, please review the background theory related to data domains. While the material may be brief, it offers a foundational understanding that will help you recognize key terms and concepts mentioned by the interviewees. This knowledge enables you to engage with the interviewee's responses in a more informed way and helps ensure that any follow-up questions or clarifications are relevant and accurate. Here it follows a list of relevant references for theoretical background:

- Systematic Literature Review on Data Mesh [3]. The paper references Domain-Driven Design (DDD) as an essential methodology for implementing data mesh principles. Specifically, DDD is applied to segment an organization's analytical data into distinct data domains that align with the structure of its business units. This alignment allows autonomous domain teams, who are closest to the data source, to manage and maintain data products relevant to their specific areas of expertise.
- Data Mesh Transition [1],
- Data Mesh by Zhamak Dehghani [2] reimagines data architecture for scaling organizations, decentralizing data ownership to domain-oriented teams like sales or finance. Each domain treats its data as a product, responsible for quality, documentation, and accessibility. The approach encourages autonomy with a self-serve infrastructure and a federated governance model, allowing consistency across the organization without central control. This model enables agile, scalable, and efficient data management by fostering domain-specific accountability and collaboration.

Fig. 1. Research Methodology Overview.

Present the introduction to the interviewee. A standard introduction has been prepared for you to share with each interviewee. You can present this introduction either just before the interview starts or at the very beginning. This introduction is designed to set expectations and clarify the interview’s purpose. Make sure to cover each point clearly, as it helps create a more relaxed environment and ensures that the interviewee understands the context of the questions they’ll be answering.

Request Additional Documentation if Mentioned. If candidates refer to specific documentation (like a list of validation criteria or supporting documents), ask if you may see them. Reviewing these can provide valuable context.

Recap Key Answers After Each Question. After the interviewee finishes responding to a question, briefly summarize their answer back to them. This helps to confirm you understood the answers correctly and to create a more organised summary.

Record and Transcribe the Interview. Ensure that each interview is recorded and transcribed for accuracy and ease of review. MS Teams is recommended, as it provides built-in recording and transcription features. Having a transcript allows you to focus more on the conversation and less on taking detailed notes, while also enabling a thorough review afterward.

Clean Up the Transcript Immediately Post-Interview. Transcripts (e.g., from MS Teams) aren’t perfect, so a quick review ensures the documentation is precise and easy to follow for

the person who synthesises the data. Right after the interview, review the transcript and make necessary edits:

- Remove filler words or phrases (e.g., "hmm," "ok," "makes sense") to keep the transcript clear and focused.
- Correct any misinterpretations and add clarifying comments where needed to accurately reflect the conversation's intent.

As you take notes or clean up the transcript, clearly label each section with the question it addresses. This makes it easy to:

- Verify all the planned questions were answered. If anything critical was missed, you can circle back to the candidate for clarification.
- Keep the documentation organised and straightforward, making it simpler for you and others to review and interpret the data.

2 Introduction

The following information should be shared with the interviewee to provide them with a clear understanding of the interview's purpose, structure, and how their responses will be used.

Introduction to the Study. This interview is part of a comprehensive research study exploring the concept of "data domains" and their implementation within data mesh architectures. Below are key points to help clarify the purpose and structure of this interview.

Part of a larger study. This interview contributes to a broader study that aims to deepen our understanding of data domains and their role in data management practices, particularly within the context of data meshes or similar architectures.

Focus on data domains in data meshes-like architectures. We are specifically interested in learning how organizations define, build, manage, and operationalize data domains within data mesh environments. This focus allows us to identify strategies, challenges, design principles and best practices across various architectures and implementations.

Global scope across major organisations. To achieve a well-rounded view, we are interviewing large organizations worldwide to understand how they approach data domains within data meshes. The diversity of insights from different industries and regions will help us gather a comprehensive picture of global practices.

Interview duration of 1 hour maximum. This interview is structured to last no longer than one hour. We aim to make the best use of this time to explore the key questions and areas of interest while respecting your schedule.

Inclusion of general information about organizations. In publishing our findings, we plan to include general information about each participating organization—such as company size, country, and industry—based on publicly available data. This context will enrich our analysis without compromising any confidential insights.

Anonymity and industry-based patterns. We will ask you some personal questions to establish statistics about the interviewees. We will not link any answers to any individual or company. However, we may highlight patterns based on industry (e.g., noting trends common to the manufacturing sector). This approach allows us to provide meaningful insights while respecting your organization's confidentiality.

Permission to record and share transcripts. We would like to record this interview, with your consent, to ensure accuracy in our analysis. The transcripts will be accessible to research colleagues involved in this study but will not be published. We value your privacy and are committed to handling this information responsibly.

3 Interview Questions

3.1 Background Info

This section is designed to set the stage for the interview by gathering key context about both the interviewer and interviewee. First, the interviewer should introduce themselves, especially if prior introductions have not been shared via email. Following this, the interviewer will invite the interviewee to introduce themselves, focusing on their current role, experience in data management, seniority level, and involvement with data mesh or domain-related initiatives within their organization. Additionally, we'll explore the organization's transition to data mesh, including its starting point. These foundational insights provide context for the conversation and help tailor questions to the interviewee's specific expertise and organizational background.

For each question is reported an example answer.

Intro. Introduce yourself (as interviewer), if you haven't shared above info already via mail before interview, introduce yourself above.

Q.1. Ask interviewee to introduce themselves:

- **Q.1.1.** Would you mind sharing your age or age range? *Answer: Age range, between 50-55.*
- **Q.1.2.** Description of their role. *Answer: Enterprise Data Architect, as being the architect of an enterprise conceptual model, that's my role.*
- **Q.1.3.** Years experience related to data management. *Answer: I've been an external consultant for 25 years. More than 10 years at this one place. Around metadata management, 8-9 years.*
- **Q.1.4.** Seniority in the organisation. *Answer: There are two people between me and the board of directors.*
- **Q.1.5.** Relation to data mesh/domains in organisation. *Answer: My role role in the data mesh is about defining the language of conceptual data. That overarching overarches domains. We found out that you need the terminology. So you need the transformation of the knowledge within the domain to exactly express what is happening in that domain in a way that other people can understand as well.*

Q.2. What does the transition in your organisation look like?

- **Q.2.1.** When did it start? *Answer: It's process running for four years now.*
- **Q.2.2.** Is there a central strategy? *Answer: Yes, my company identified a couple of strategic programs and our program called unlock data is one of those top strategic programs.*

3.2 Data Domain Characteristics in the Organisation

This section dives into the practical implementation of data domains within the interviewee's organization. The goal is to understand how data domains are structured and whether these structures align across different organizations. We begin by exploring what data domains look like in their specific context, seeking details on the number, size, and scale of these domains, including examples when possible. Next, we look at the relationship between data domains and established business and IT structures. This includes examining how data domains interact with or diverge from existing business and IT hierarchies, their alignment (business, IT, or otherwise), and the

level of decentralization in the organization's approach. This context helps identify patterns and distinctions in domain structures across organizations.

Q.3. What do domains typically look like in your organisation?

- **Q.3.1.** Can you give an example? *Answer: A network department is also responsible for sales. Now it's the different business process the responsibility areas.*
- **Q.3.2.** How many domains are you aiming for? *Answer: So we tried to keep it manageable at least also from a governance point of view because you couldn't create very small domains. Our company has 4 segments: we would end up with roughly 40 domains, 10 per segment.*
- **Q.3.3.** How big is each domain? *Answer: For each domain, we will probably end up with one data integration team. And then normally they also have an BI and analytics team associated to it. All the IT systems are theoretically part of the domain. And also perhaps even the business people because we're combining business and data and IT in a domain.*
 - In terms of people/teams?
 - In terms of data?
 - In terms of roles?
 - In terms of business processes/capabilities?

Q.4. How do your domains relate to business and IT?

- **Q.4.1.** Many organisations already have well-defined business hierarchies and IT hierarchies. Do you have these? *Answer: yes.*
- **Q.4.2.** Are your data domains following these existing hierarchies? What is the relation between them? *Answer: IT and businesses are sometimes quite far from each other. We have IT systems with their own hierarchy and business processes with their own hierarchies. And there might be some overlap, but it's not perfectly one-on-one.*
- **Q.4.3.** Is a data domain IT-aligned? Is it Business-aligned? Middle? Neither? If neither, how? *Answer: It's aligned to the business process, but a process needs IT and people. It's always in a triangle.*
- **Q.4.4.** How decentralised are your domains? *Answer: (i) They are really headed, often something that's already organised as a department. They already have their own BI team, some even actually have their own data team already. (ii) Operationally they are not independent. A domain is always connected to the rest of your company.*

3.3 Data Domain Definition

This section aims to clarify how data domains are understood and defined within the organization, as definitions can often be vague or inconsistent. We begin by asking whether there is a formal definition of a data domain within the organization and, if the interviewee does not have one at hand, what characteristics or components the interviewee believes define a data domain. Key points of interest include both technical and organizational components or constraints associated with domains, the positioning of data domains relative to business and IT functions, and the roles involved in domain management. Specifically, we explore whether the organization assigns roles like domain owners, data product owners, or data stewards, and where these roles are typically sourced (business, IT, or cross-functional). Additionally, we inquire if any particular theoretical frameworks guide the definition of data domains and who within the organization is (or should be) responsible for defining them. This section provides valuable insights into the foundational concepts and structures around data domains in practice.

Q.5. Do you have a formal definition of a data domain in your organisation? If not, can you tell us what you think defines a data domain? *Answer: What we consider a domain is a business*

capability or a set of business capabilities consisting of a number of processes, IT systems and a set of data that support. An important business function so that can be assurance billing.

- **Q.5.1.** Which technical components/restraints are associated with a domain? *Answer: For instance, we have a domain billing and then we look where which processors are then responsibility of billing, which IT systems are part are supporting to that process and then which data are then part of that.*
- **Q.5.2.** Which organisational components/restraints are associated with a domain? *Answer: A domain is a set of of related business processes which makes sense to organize in a way that you can do operational and analytical. It has the IT infrastructure to support it and the data models and infrastructure to support that. But it's not dedicated. The operations are not dedicated to domain because you cannot organize that.*
- **Q.5.3.** How is this domain positioned between IT domains and business domains? (can skip if already answered previously). *Answer: In service-oriented domains, follow the business. In resource-oriented domains, follow the resources.*
- **Q.5.4.** Do you follow a certain theory to define your domains? If so, which one? *Answer: The theory comes from Zhamak and from Pietheine Strengholt book. Those are the bigger inspirations*
- **Q.5.5.** Related to that, what roles are involved in domains? Or assigned to domains? For example, are there domain owners (or domain data owners)? Data product owners? Data stewards? Are these exclusive to domains, or do they overlap? Who is generally asked to fill these roles? Is it people from business? From IT? People with domain knowledge or people with IT knowledge? High-level? On the bridge between central teams and decentral teams? *Answer: The first rule of data mesh is that you organize ownership by domains. If you put business processes as leading entities to to define the domains, then there should be somebody owner of those processes. In my opinion, the business should be in the lead: so there should be a business owner. I believe very much in the importance of data stewards as the people that actually look at the quality of the data both in the domain incoming in the domain and also together with those data product owners.*
- **Q.5.6.** Who is/should be providing the definition of a domain? *Answer: the domains themselves are in charge of defining domains, they get support from more centralized roles such as process managers. And there's a translation expert in between who can speak both the language of the process managers or the centralized architects and of the domain and and match these expectations.*
- **Q.5.7.** Should domain boundaries be fluid? If yes, how fluid? Why? *Answer: Fluid not, not really fluid but you cannot say this is mine without asking another one, which is on the same topic.*

3.4 Data Domain Creation Process

This section explores the practical processes involved in creating data domains within the organization, addressing a relatively unexplored area in existing literature. We begin by understanding the purpose behind establishing data domains, whether they address specific organizational challenges, support business processes, or enhance IT functions. We then examine the prioritization process, the roles involved, and how business and IT support the domain creation efforts. Key decision points, such as approval processes, performance indicators, and validation criteria, are also discussed to understand how organizations measure success and completion for each domain. Finally, we inquire about the number of domains that have been set up in this manner to assess the organization's overall progress and approach to scaling domains.

Q.6. How does your organisation set up data domains?

- **Q.6.1.** Why does your organisation set-up domains? What problem are they intended to solve? Do they support business processes? IT functions? *Answer: it's about setting up these organizational units where everyone can speak the same language and understand everything more or less that's going on within the domain.*
- **Q.6.2.** How do you prioritise which data domains to set up first? *Answer: We have the VRO and there's no output from the VRO. In theory, the value realization office prioritizes. Prioritizing domains is also finding people who are willing to invest time and effort and solve the problem that they have.*
- **Q.6.3.** Which people are involved in setting-up your domain? How do the business and IT support the domains? *Answer: the domain owner, the data domain architect and the centralized support.*
- **Q.6.4.** Who approves the domain? *Answer: The Central Data Office.*
- **Q.6.5.** Do you have KPI's for your domain? Is there a definition of done? Validation criteria? *Answer: There is a set of things that we have been doing, as a bunch of dots related to each other that actually go from the defining domain to the maturity of domain. So there is some theoretical idea about that, but there is no actual.*
- **Q.6.6.** Do you have steps to follow when you setup domains? Can you briefly describe your process? *Answer: Yes. You first detect. You have the priority, you have your value realization office that says we are going to do this in that domain or and we have a good reason for that. Then you of course need to find the people that have knowledge about this topic. Then, need operational people. Then you are starting to actually define the processes. If we have those processes. What kind of applications are supporting your processes and what kind of data is created in that processes? And then you actually fill your domain, what we call it, the boundaries of your domain based on data.*
- **Q.6.7.** How many domains have you set up this way? *Answer: We have more or less 3 domains.*

3.5 Learnings

This section focuses on capturing the interviewee's thoughts on their organization's journey with data domains, highlighting valuable insights gained from their experiences. We begin by discussing what went well in the domain implementation process, as well as any recommendations they would offer to other organizations pursuing similar goals. We also explore areas that did not go as planned, including any solutions developed to address these issues. Additionally, we seek insights on gaps in current theory and research, inviting suggestions on specific challenges that would benefit from academic exploration. Lastly, we ask whether common challenges are observed across domains or if each domain presents unique obstacles, helping to identify any recurring patterns or distinctive issues in domain management.

Q.7. Having discussed all of the above, what do you think are your key learnings?

- **Q.7.1.** What went well? *Answer: This is all theoretically boundaries where we have sometimes a lot of and because if there are not the right people on the table, you can take a long time to do this. If you have the right people, my experience is that you can do it much faster.*
- **Q.7.2.** What would you recommend to other organisations? *Answer: start small and grow bigger. Strong focus on why you want to do this for this particular part of the company because and then communicate that to the rest of the company.*
- **Q.7.3.** What did not go well? *Answer: defining the domain borders. if you follow the architect, the business doesn't understand at all what they're talking about. And when you follow the business too much then you have to risk of the lines actually not being clear enough with the risk.*

– Have you solved this?

- **Q.7.4.** Do you see any open challenges? *Answer: OPEN ANSWER.*

Q.8. Are there common challenges between domains that arise, or each domain present its own challenges? *Answer: I can rather imagine that it's quite dependent per domain.*

Q.9. What would you like from theory? Is there a problem/challenge that science should look into? *Answer: It's a triangle between people it and process. If you know that from an organization, then you put them in the model.*

Q.10. Would you be available for a follow-up interview in a year? *Answer: Yes.*

3.6 Wrap-up

Q.11. Are there any additional insights or examples you would like to share about your experience with data domains? *Answer: bottom up without top down is not working. These kind of changes should be totally understood by the top management and also driven by a top manager. And if not then its bottom up is not OK enough. I think if you miss bottom up, you never get anything done.*

4 List of Interview Questions

You can refer to the provided question list page during the interview to keep track of the questions you've covered. Mark off each question as it's answered to ensure nothing important is missed.

Background Info

Intro. Introduce yourself (as interviewer), if you haven't shared above info already via mail before interview, introduce yourself above.

Q.1. Ask interviewee to introduce themselves:

- **Q.1.1.** Would you mind sharing your age or age range?
- **Q.1.2.** Description of their role.
- **Q.1.3.** Years experience related to data management.
- **Q.1.4.** Seniority in the organisation.
- **Q.1.5.** Relation to data mesh/domains in organisation.

Q.2. What does the transition in your organisation look like?

- **Q.2.1.** When did it start?
- **Q.2.2.** Is there a central strategy?

Data Domain Characteristics in the Organisation

Q.3. What do domains typically look like in your organisation?

- **Q.3.1.** Can you give an example?
- **Q.3.2.** How many domains are you aiming for?
- **Q.3.3.** How big is each domain?
 - In terms of people/teams?
 - In terms of data?
 - In terms of roles?
 - In terms of business processes/capabilities?

Q.4. How do your domains relate to business and IT?

- **Q.4.1.** Many organisations already have well-defined business hierarchies and IT hierarchies. Do you have these?
- **Q.4.2.** Are your data domains following these existing hierarchies? What is the relation between them?
- **Q.4.3.** Is a data domain IT-aligned? Is it Business-aligned? Middle? Neither? If neither, how?
- **Q.4.4.** How decentralised are your domains?

Data Domain Definition

Q.5. Do you have a formal definition of a data domain in your organisation? If not, can you tell us what you think defines a data domain?

- **Q.5.1.** Which technical components/restraints are associated with a domain?
- **Q.5.2.** Which organisational components/restraints are associated with a domain?
- **Q.5.3.** How is this domain positioned between IT domains and business domains? (can skip if already answered previously).
- **Q.5.4.** Do you follow a certain theory to define your domains? If so, which one?
- **Q.5.5.** Related to that, what roles are involved in domains? Or assigned to domains? For example, are there domain owners (or domain data owners)? Data product owners? Data stewards? Are these exclusive to domains, or do they overlap? Who is generally asked to fill

these roles? Is it people from business? From IT? People with domain knowledge or people with IT knowledge? High-level? On the bridge between central teams and decentral teams?

- Q.5.6. Who is/should be providing the definition of a domain?
- Q.5.7. Should domain boundaries be fluid? If yes, how fluid? Why?

Data Domain Creation Process

Q.6. How does your organisation set up data domains?

- Q.6.1. Why does your organisation set-up domains? What problem are they intended to solve? Do they support business processes? IT functions?
- Q.6.2. How do you prioritise which data domains to set up first?
- Q.6.3. Which people are involved in setting-up your domain? How do the business and IT support the domains?
- Q.6.4. Who approves the domain?
- Q.6.5. Do you have KPI's for your domain? Is there a definition of done? Validation criteria?
- Q.6.6. Do you have steps to follow when you setup domains? Can you briefly describe your process?
- Q.6.7. How many domains have you set up this way?

Learnings

Q.7. Having discussed all of the above, what do you think are your key learnings?

- Q.7.1. What went well?
- Q.7.2. What would you recommend to other organisations?
- Q.7.3. What did not go well?
 - Have you solved this?
- Q.7.4. Do you see any open challenges?

Q.8. Are there common challenges between domains that arise, or each domain present its own challenges?

Q.9. What would you like from theory? Is there a problem/challenge that science should look into?

Q.10. Would you be available for a follow-up interview in a year?

Wrap-up

Q.11. Are there any additional insights or examples you would like to share about your experience with data domains?

References

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